

Schmidt reaction of *trans*-3-benzylflavanones : Formation of 3-benzyl-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazepin-5(4*H*)ones having both *cis* and *trans* configurations

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Abstract : On treatment with $\text{NaN}_3/\text{c.H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-HOAc}$, *trans*-3-benzylflavanones yield ring expansion products with alkyl migration and having either *cis* or both *cis* and *trans* configurations.

Keywords : *trans*-3-Benzylflavanones, Schmidt reaction, *cis* and *trans*-3-benzyl-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazepin-5(4*H*)ones.

Introduction

It is well-established that Schmidt rearrangement of chromanones produces 2,3-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazepin-5(4*H*)ones as major product by preferential alkyl migration¹⁻⁴. The chromanones used so far for this rearrangement are either 2,3-unsubstituted or 2- or 3-substituted. 2,3-Disubstituted chromanones can exist in two isomeric forms viz. *cis* and *trans*. In continuation of our current studies on Schmidt reaction⁵⁻⁷, we became interested to study the Schmidt rearrangement of such compounds to see whether the *cis* or *trans* stereochemistry of the starting materials is retained in the product or that is changed during the reaction.

Results and discussion

trans-3-Benzylflavanones (1) were chosen to be suitable substrates for starting the proposed study as these

compounds could be obtained readily from *E*-3-benzylidene flavanones by the route shown in Scheme 1. Preparation of 1a and 1b were done by oxidation of 3(*S**)-benzyl-4(*S**)-hydroxy-2(*S**)flavans (2a and 2b) with chromic acid while that of 1c by oxidation of 2c with active manganese dioxide^{8,9} as in this case chromic acid oxidation resulted in the formation of *trans*-3-(*p*-methoxybenzoyl)flavanone (4) even at 0 °C¹⁰.

All the three starting *trans*-3-benzylflavanones (1a-c) were viscous liquids. They were subjected to Schmidt reaction condition using $\text{NaN}_3/\text{c.H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-HOAc}$ at 55 °C temperature. The reaction was found to be complete within 12 h yielding in each case a product showing a single spot in TLC. The ¹H NMR spectra of these products, however, showed that only the product from 1b was a pure compound having *cis* configuration (5b) while those from 1a and 1c were mixtures of *cis* and *trans* compounds

Scheme 1

(5 and 6) in which the *cis* product was the major component as evident from ^1H NMR spectral features. Attempted separation of the *cis* and *trans* products from the mixture by chromatography (both column and preparative thin layer) over silica gel as well as by fractional crystallization did not meet with success.

on a Bruker AM-300L (300 MHz) spectrometer.

Preparation of the trans-3-benzylflavanones 1a and 1b :

To a solution of 3(*S*^{*})-benzyl-4(*S*^{*})-hydroxy-2(*S*^{*})flavans (2) (250 mg) [obtained by sodium borohydride reduction¹² of *E*-3-benzylidene flavanones (3)] in acetic acid (10 ml), CrO_3 (400 mg) was added and the

a : R = H; b : R = Cl; c : R = OMe

It may be mentioned here that ketones of the type $\text{RCOCHR}^1\text{R}^2\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ ($\text{R}^1 \neq \text{H}$; $\text{R}^2 \neq \text{H}$) having chirality at the α -position undergo rearrangement with retention of configuration¹¹. So, in order to rationalize the formation of *cis* product as only/major product in this case, pure *trans*-3-benzylflavanones (1) was treated with only $\text{c.H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-HOAc}$ for 12 h at 55 °C temperature and after usual work up ^1H NMR spectral studies were done. Such studies revealed that *trans*-3-benzylflavanones (1) changed to a significant extent (*ca.* 30%) to the *cis* compound. So the processes which are possibly taking place are isomerisation of 1 followed by rearrangement of the individual isomers. Thus, in the equilibrium *trans*-3-benzylflavanones \rightleftharpoons *cis*-3-benzylflavanones, the latter is less populated because of its less stability, but possibly it undergoes rearrangement at a much faster rate giving *cis*-2,3-disubstituted 2,3-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazepin-5(4*H*)one as either the major product or the only product.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in chloroform (unless otherwise stated) on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer, ^1H NMR spectra in CDCl_3

mixture was stirred and allowed to stand for 30 min at room temperature. The crude reaction product was then chromatographed over silica gel using ethyl acetate-petrol (5 : 95) as eluent to get colourless pure liquid product in very good yield.

Preparation of the trans-3-benzylflavanone 1c :

A solution of 2c (1 mmol) in chloroform (20 ml) was stirred with active manganese dioxide^{8,9} (10 g) at room temperature for 24 h. Then it was filtered through a fluted filter paper and the filtrate was concentrated. The concentrated material on column chromatography over silica gel gave pure 1c as liquid product in good yield.

The IR and ^1H NMR spectral data of all the *trans*-3-benzylflavanones (1a-c) were as follows :

1a : A viscous liquid, yield : 80%, IR : 1680 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); ^1H NMR : δ 2.95 (1H, dd, J 14.1 as 6.3 Hz, H_a of CH_2Ph), 3.03 (1H, dd, J 14.1 as 5.7 Hz, H_b of CH_2Ph), 3.36 (1H, m, H-3), 5.27 (1H, d, J 8.7 Hz, H-2), 6.92–7.08 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.15–7.24 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.30–7.36 (5H, m, Ar-H, one Ph), 7.48 (1H, ddd, J 8.1, 7.8 and 1.54 Hz, H-7) and 7.90 (1H, dd, J 7.8 and 1.2 Hz, H-5).

1b : A viscous liquid, yield : 72%, IR : 1675 cm^{-1} (C=O); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 2.89 (1H, dd, J 14.1 and 5.7 Hz, H_a of CH_2Ph), 2.99 (1H, dd, J 14.1 and 5.7 Hz, H_b of CH_2Ph), 3.33 (1H, m, H-3), 5.20 (1H, d, J 9.6 Hz, H-2), 6.98–7.16 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.33–7.36 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.48 (1H, ddd, J 7.8, 6.0 and 1.5 Hz, H-7) and 7.90 (1H, dd, J 6.0 and 1.5 Hz, H-5).

1c : A viscous liquid, yield : 63%, IR : 1682 cm^{-1} (C=O); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 2.90 (1H, dd, J 14.4 and 6.3 Hz, H_a of CH_2Ph), 2.97 (1H, dd, J 14.1, 8.1 Hz, H_b of CH_2Ph), 3.32 (1H, m, H-3), 3.76 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.26 (1H, d, J 8.7 Hz, H-2), 6.76 (2H, pattern resembles a pair of triplets¹³, J 8.7 and 2.7 or 1.8 Hz, H-2'',6''), 6.98–7.04 (4H, m, H-3'',5'',6,8), 7.33–7.34 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.48 (1H, ddd, J 8.1, 7.8 and 1.5 Hz, H-7) and 7.89 (1H, dd, J 7.8 and 1.5 Hz, H-5).

General procedure for the reaction of trans-3-benzylflavanone with $\text{NaN}_3/\text{c.H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{HOAc}$:

Appropriate *trans*-3-benzylflavanone (0.5 mmol) was dissolved in $\text{c.H}_2\text{SO}_4$ -HOAc mixture (1 : 5, 6 ml) within 0–10 °C and to the cold solution sodium azide (1 mmol) was added in three equal portions with stirring. The resulting mixture was then heated at 55 °C for 12 h. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was diluted with water and extracted with chloroform (3 \times 25 ml). The chloroform layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated. Chromatography of the concentrate over silica gel furnished the product in moderate yield.

Products from **1a** and **1c** were mixtures of *cis* and *trans* compounds (**5** and **6** in the approximate ratio 9 : 1) as evident from $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectral data [**5a** : H-2, δ 5.34 (d, J 3 Hz), N-H, δ 6.14 (d, J 5.7 Hz); **6a** : H-2, δ 5.23 (d, J 10.0 Hz), N-H, δ 6.28 (d, J 3.4 Hz) and **5c** : OCH_3 , δ 3.76 (s), H-2, δ 5.33 (d, J 3.0 Hz), N-H, δ 5.83 (d, J 5.4 Hz); **6c** : OCH_3 , δ 3.78 (s), H-2, δ 5.20 (d, J 9.6 Hz), N-H, δ 5.98 (d, J 3.4 Hz)] and that from **1b** was a pure *cis*-2,3-disubstituted 2,3-dihydro-1,4-benzoxazepin-5(4H)one (**5b**) (colourless needles). The analytical and spectral data of **5b** were as follows :

5b : m.p. 176–177 °C, IR : 3398 (N-H), 1648 cm^{-1} (C=O); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 2.31 (1H, dd, J 14.4 and 11.4 Hz, H_a of CH_2Ph), 2.74 (1H, dd, J 14.4 and 3.9 Hz, H_b of CH_2Ph), 4.03 (1H, m, multiplicity decreased on D_2O

shaking, H-3), 5.33 (1H, d, J 3.0 Hz, H-2), 6.32 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, exchangeable with D_2O , N-H), 6.93 (2H, d, J 1.2 Hz, H-2'',6''), 7.15–7.25 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.42–7.54 (6H, m, Ar-H) and 7.93 (1H, dd, J 7.8 and 1.2 Hz, H-6); EIMS : m/z 365 and 363 (M^{*+}) (Found : C, 72.42; H, 5.17; N, 3.43. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_2\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 72.61; H, 4.99; N, 3.85%).

Spectral data of compound **4** : IR (KBr) : 1685 (C=O) and 1665 cm^{-1} (C=O); $^1\text{H NMR}$: δ 3.85 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.06 (1H, d, J 12 Hz, H-3), 6.00 (1H, d, J 12 Hz, H-2), 6.88 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-2'',6''), 7.07–7.10 (2H, m, H-6,8), 7.28–7.50 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.56 (1H, H-7), 7.80 (2H, d, J 7.80 Hz, H-3'',5'') and 7.93 (1H, H-5).

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